

RIS Synergy: Standardised Data Exchange in Research Administration

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Funded by the BMBWF and carried out between 2020 and 2024, RIS Synergy brought together 14 Austrian universities and four national funding agencies to establish automated exchange mechanisms for metadata across systems of funders and research institutions. The project focused on developing shared interfaces, tools and standardised metadata models – enabling more efficient workflows, improved metadata quality and better integration between institutions. Tools such as the Import Tool and FUNDiFy are being further developed under ARI&Snet and form a sustainable foundation for the digital transformation of Austria’s research landscape.

From 2020 to the end of 2024, the BMBWF-funded [RIS Synergy](#) project, coordinated by TU Wien, brought together [14 Austrian universities and four national funding agencies](#) to streamline research-related processes and establish automated metadata exchange between systems. The project focused on the development of standardised interfaces, metadata models and digital services. The advancement of metadata standards for research information exchange was a shared effort across the consortium and served as a basis for many of the project’s results. The official closing event of the consortium took place on [5 March 2025](#) in Vienna.

Tools and Interfaces for Metadata Exchange

One core outcome was the development of the [Import Tool](#), which supports the automatic exchange of project and application metadata between funders and institutional systems.

Alongside it, the [FUNDiFy](#) tool was developed to manage and share programme information in a structured and standardised way. Both applications were developed by the project consortium and are approaching production status. These tools help reduce manual data entry and

improve data quality throughout the [research lifecycle](#).

As part of RIS Synergy, several universities set up and configured their research information system to enable metadata harvesting via the existing [OAI-PMH interface](#) provided by [OpenAIRE](#). This made publication metadata available in a standardised, machine-readable format, allowing OpenAIRE to harvest it and enabling funders such as the FWF to retrieve this data directly from the platform – supporting the once-only principle by reducing duplicate data entry.

RIS Synergy also developed a standardised [organisational chart interface](#), which made it possible for the FFG to roll out its new master account system for universities. This allows institutions to manage project access more efficiently, with centralised oversight and role-based permissions.

In addition, plugins were developed to support the integration of FUNDiFy into institutional websites, making it easier to use programme information internally.

Strategic Outcomes and Next Steps

A strategic outcome was the [concept study for a national research portal](#), which defined the key conditions and

requirements for a centralised platform. While no unified recommendation for implementation was made, structured metadata exchange was clearly identified as a necessary foundation for future developments in this area – nationally and in the broader European context.

In addition to the final project event, RIS Synergy hosted [CRIS2024](#), the international conference on research information systems organised by [euroCRIS](#), TU Wien, and the University of Vienna. The project contributed several presentations, including an award-winning poster.

Although RIS Synergy officially ended in 2024, components such as the Import Tool

and [FUNDify](#) continue to be developed – through the [ARI&Snet](#) framework and largely through in-kind contributions from the project partners. All former project partners remain actively involved in maintaining and improving the shared tools and standards.

With its focus on interoperability, metadata quality and collaboration between institutions and funders, RIS Synergy supports the alignment of Austria's infrastructure with European initiatives such as EOSC and contributes to a more connected, transparent, and efficient research environment. Its results also support the broader implementation of FAIR data principles.

Graphic Recording by Lana Lauren at CRIS2024 – www.lanalauren.com